

Online Supplement

Manuscript Number: DSR1-D-23-00160

**Wooden steps to shallow depths: a new bathymodiolin mussel, *Vadumodiolus teredinicola*,
inhabits shipworm burrows in an ancient submarine forest**

Marvin A. Altamia¹, Hannah J. Appiah-Madson¹, Rosalia Falco Poulin¹, Bruno Huettel², Maxim
Rubin-Blum³, Nicole Dubilier⁴, Harald R. Gruber-Vodicka^{4,5}, Nikolaus Leisch⁶, and Daniel L.
Distel^{1*}

Affiliations

¹Ocean Genome Legacy Center, Department of Marine and Environmental Science,
Northeastern University, Nahant, MA, USA

²Max Planck Genome Centre Cologne, Max Planck Institute for Plant Breeding Research,
Cologne, Germany

³Israel Oceanographic and Limnological Research Institute– IOLR, Haifa, Israel

⁴Max Planck Institute for Marine Microbiology, Bremen, Germany

⁵Marine Symbiosis Group, Zoological Institute, Christian-Albrechts-University, Kiel, Germany

⁶EMBL Heidelberg, Heidelberg, Germany

*Corresponding author d.distel@northeastern.edu

Keywords: Bathymodiolinae, Bivalve evolution, Chemoautotrophic symbiosis, Mytilidae, Teredinidae, Thioautotrophic symbionts

Supplementary Figures

Supplementary Figure SF1: Deployed and naturally occurring wood at the Alabama Undersea Forest (AUF) site. (a) Experimental collection panel constructed of two lengths of bald cypress lumber and one roughewn log. (b) Collection panel deployed at the AUF site. (c) Naturally occurring ancient wood exposed on the sea floor at the AUF site.

Supplementary Figure SF2. Length and height measurements for the valves of the *Vadumodiolus teredinicola* type series. Scatter plot showing length (x-axis) and height (y-axis) of valves in mm for 21 specimens of *V. teredinicola* collected from a bald cypress log exposed for 8 months at the Alabama Undersea Forest site. Numerical values and associated specimen data are shown in Supplementary Table ST2.

Supplementary Figure SF3. Female and male specimens of *Vadumodiolus teredinicola*. (a) female specimen, (b) male specimen, (c–d) hematoxylin- and eosin-stained transverse sections through the visceral mass and gills of a (c) female and (d) male specimen, (e) detail of the box in (c), (f) detail of the box in (d). Arrows in (e) and (f) indicate mature oocytes and sperm cells,

respectively. Note that the fragile valves in (a) are broken. Scale bars, (a, b) 5.0 mm, (c, d) 500 μm , (e, f) 40 μm .

Supplementary Figure SF4: Phylogram depicting the inferred relationships among *Vadumodolius teredinicola* gill bacterium and related symbionts based on 16S rRNA sequences. Sequences were aligned using MAFFT auto algorithm with the scoring matrix 200PAM / k-2, gap open penalty of 1.53 and offset value of 0.123. Aligned sequences were trimmed to 1,314 bp. The phylogram presented is a Bayesian tree employing GTR+I+ Γ as the substitution model in MrBayes version 3.2.6. A maximum-likelihood tree was also constructed using IQ-Tree2 with GTR+I+ Γ as the substitution model. Posterior probability values greater than 0.90 are displayed to the left of the slash at associated nodes. To the right of the slash are bootstrap proportions greater than 70% of 1,000 replicates for nodes also supported by the maximum likelihood analysis (iQ-Tree v2.2). Scale bar = 0.1 substitutions per 100 base pairs. NCBI accession numbers for symbionts known only by their 16S rRNA sequences are indicated at the end of taxon name.

Supplementary Figure SF5: Phylogram depicting the inferred relationships among three *Vadumodiolus teredinicola* gill bacterium metagenome-assembled genome assemblies and related symbionts based conserved protein markers. The Genome Taxonomy Database Tool Kit was used to identify, extract, and align the protein markers in the genome assemblies. The maximum likelihood tree was constructed using RAxML. Bootstrap proportions greater than 70% of 1,000 replicates are indicated for each node. The scale bar represents the substitution rate per site. Note that the *V. teredinicola* genome assemblies obtained by Metabat2 binning, BLAST searches, and a combination of both, are indistinguishable in this analysis.

a

ANI Matrix (above) / AAI Matrix (below)	<i>V. teredinicola</i>	<i>B. azoricus</i>	<i>B. septemdiarium</i>	<i>B. thermophilus</i>	<i>Ca. T. autotrophica</i>	<i>Ca. R. magnifica</i>	<i>Ca. V. okutanii</i>	<i>Ca. V. endoextente</i>
<i>V. teredinicola</i> gill bacterium		81	77	79	77	77	77	77
<i>B. azoricus</i> symbiont	82		78	80	77	77	77	77
<i>B. septemdiarium</i> symbiont	77	77		79	77	76	77	77
<i>B. thermophilus</i> symbiont	78	77	77		77	76	77	77
<i>Ca. Thioglobus autotrophica</i>	73	71	72	71		77	76	76
<i>Ca. Ruthia magnifica</i>	72	72	72	72	74		83	83
<i>Ca. Vesicomysocius okutanii</i>	70	71	70	71	73	83		94
<i>Ca. Vesicomysocius endoextente</i>	70	71	70	71	72	82	95	

b

Supplementary Figure SF6: Comparison of the *Vadumodiolus teredinicola* gill bacterium metagenome-assembled genome (MAG) with other bathymodiolin symbiont MAGs. (a)

Heat map showing comparisons of genomic average nucleotide identity (ANI; above the diagonal) and average amino identity acid (AAI; below the diagonal) among bathymodiolin symbionts and related bacteria. Color scale is from green (lowest) to red (highest). (b) ANI-distance clustering based on the Ward method. Note that the *V. teredinicola* gill bacterium clusters with other bathymodiolin thioautotrophic symbionts. (c) Alignment of coding sequences identified in the *V. teredinicola* gill bacterium MAG (magenta) with the MAG of *Bathymodiolus septemdierum* Myojin Knoll symbiont closed-circular genome (blue).

Supplementary Figure SF7: Confocal laser scanning microscopy overview of the symbionts of *Vadumodiolus teredinicola* using antisense probes. Dual-probe fluorescence *in situ* hybridization (FISH) using 16S rRNA antisense probes Cy5-EUB338NON (red) and Cy3-EUB338NON (green). DNA is stained with NucBlue Nuclear Stain (white). (a) Transverse section through the gill and visceral mass of a mature male specimen of *V. teredinicola*, (b) detail of the boxed region in (a), (c) detail of the boxed region in (b). Note the absence of antisense probe signals in the gill bacteria (boxed regions). Autofluorescence is observed in the cuticle secretory vesicles (csv) in the foot and granulocytes (gra) in the gills. Scale bar, (a) 500 μ m; (b) 50 μ m, (c) 5 μ m.

Supplementary Figure SF8. Specimens of *Vadumodiolus teredinicola* showing green pigmented material within the stomach. Scale bar, 2.0 mm.

Supplementary Figure SF9: Specimens of *Vadumodiolus teredinicola* in abandoned shipworm burrows. The left sides of the burrow walls have been removed to show the specimens in life position within the burrows. Black arrows indicate *V. teredinicola* specimens. White arrows indicate the remaining pallets of *Bankia gouldi*, the shipworm species that created and inhabited the burrows previously. Scale bar, 5.0 mm.

Supplementary Videos

Supplementary Video SV1. Animation demonstrating the anatomy of *Vadumodiolus teredinicola* as visualized by microcomputed tomography. Animation shows 830 virtual transverse sections through a specimen of *V. teredinicola*. Sections are spaced at intervals of approximately 9.6 μm and are ordered from posterior to anterior. The specimen is approximately 8.59 mm in length and appears in frames 86–916. Video may be found at https://datadryad.org/stash/share/HaE12zZB1mSEZy0lMge2zsUe7KGH2Eb24L5_7HGypIo.

Vadumodiolus teredinicola

Northeastern University

Vadumodiolus teredinicola Supplemental Video SV2 v2

Supplementary Video SV2. Motility of *Vadumodiolus teredinicola*. Specimens of *V.*

teredinicola are highly mobile via a long prehensile foot, capable of extending at least one body length beyond the anterior edge of the valves. The distal end of the foot forms a muscular disk- or shield-shaped surface that can grasp both rough and smooth surfaces. By repeatedly extending the foot, attaching the tip to surfaces, and contracting the foot, individuals can rapidly crawl over surfaces. Video may be found at

https://datadryad.org/stash/share/HaE12zZB1mSEZy0lMge2zsUe7KGH2Eb24L5_7HGypIo.

Metagenome assembly details

To search for evidence of bacterial symbionts in the tissues of *Vadumodiolus teredinicola*, we sequenced the gill metagenomes of three specimens, assembled contigs and sorted contigs of predicted bacterial origin into bins reflecting individual predicted bacterial MAGs using SPADes and metaBAT2. Reads of bacterial origin were sparsely represented in the three individual gill metagenome datasets. However, by combining reads from all three gill metagenome sequences during SPADes assembly, a single, though highly fragmented, bacterial MAG was assembled. MetaBAT2 uses tetranucleotide composition information to perform binning. MetaBAT2 takes a metagenome assembly and the reads that produced the assembly and organizes the contigs into putative genomes, called "bins". Because metaBAT2 only uses contigs longer than 1.5 kbp during binning, we performed BLASTn searches using the 16S rRNA genes, 23S rRNA genes, and coding sequences (CDS) of *B. thermophilus* thioautotrophic gill symbiont strain EPR9N to recruit un-binned short bacterial contigs in the assembled metagenome. A maximum likelihood phylogenetic analysis (RAxML) based on a set of 120 conserved bacterial genes identified and aligned using GTDB-tk (Chaumeil *et al.*, 2019) showed that the metaBAT2 bin and the contigs identified with BLAST searches are nearly identical and that they form a well-supported clade (100% bootstrap support, 1,000 replicates) with symbiont genomes determined for *Bathymodiolus azoricus*, *B. septemdiarum*, and *B. thermophilus* (Supplementary Table ST2-4, Supplementary Figure SF6. Because the metaBAT2 binned bacterial contigs and concatenated contigs obtained using BLAST searches are phylogenetically indistinguishable, it is reasonable to assume that they represent the same bacterial genome present in the gills and thus can be

combined to create a more complete assembly. The final assembly is composed of 611 contigs with a total size of 1,060,823 bp and a %GC content of 38.4%. The *V. teredinicola* gill bacterial final draft genome assembly is highly fragmented with an N50 of just 2.3 kbp, nevertheless it is estimated to be 87.88% complete with an acceptable level of contamination of just 2.82% (Supplementary Table ST2). The draft *V. teredinicola* gill bacterium MAG is deposited online at NCBI as WGS Assembly under accession number JASISB000000000 (BioSample SAMN35084530, BioProject PRJNA964767).

In most instances, rRNA genes cannot be recovered in the metagenomes if there is a complex community present. However, in *V. teredinicola*, both near full-length 16S and 23S rRNA genes can be recovered indicating that the gill microbial community is composed of a single symbiont ribotype. This is similar to what has been observed in *B. septemdiarum* and *B. thermophilus* wherein only 1 type of thioautotrophic symbiont is present. We identified homologs of sulfide-quinone reductase (*sqr*), adenylylsulfate reductase subunit alpha (*aprA*), and small and large-subunits of ribulose-1,5-bisphosphate carboxylase/oxygenase (RuBisCO) (*cbbS* and *cbbL*) in the genome assembly, signifying that the *V. teredinicola* gill bacterium is a thioautotroph, like many bathymodiolin symbionts (Supplementary Table ST3).

Supplementary Tables

Supplementary Table ST1: GenBank accession records for taxa and genes used in this study.

Subfamily	Genus	Species	18S rRNA accession	28S rRNA accession	16S rRNA accession	COI accession
Bathymodiolinae	<i>Vadumodiolus</i>	<i>teredinicola</i>	OQ919029	OQ919032	OQ920280	OQ915218
Bathymodiolinae	<i>Idas</i>	<i>modiolaeformis</i> PD Med 12	OQ919030	OQ919033	OQ920281	OQ915219
Bathymodiolinae	<i>Idas</i>	<i>modiolaeformis</i> PD Med 15	OQ919031	OQ919034	OQ920282	OQ915220
Bathymodiolinae	<i>Idas</i>	<i>macdonaldi</i>	AF221647	AY781145	HF545092	AY649804
Bathymodiolinae	<i>Idas</i>	<i>modiolaeformis</i>	KF611730	FJ159555	KF611772	FJ158585
Bathymodiolinae	<i>Adipicola</i>	<i>iwaotakii</i> A"	KF611729	EU683288	KF611770	EU702333
Bathymodiolinae	<i>Idas</i>	ESU N	KF611728	GU065843	KF611769	FJ937205
Bathymodiolinae	<i>Idas</i>	sp. D	KF611724	EU683275	KF611765	EU702357
Bathymodiolinae	<i>Idas</i>	sp. C	KF611725	EU683260	KF611766	EU702376
Bathymodiolinae	<i>Idas</i>	ESU M	KF611726	GU065845	KF611767	FJ937202
Bathymodiolinae	<i>Idas</i>	ESU L	KF611727	GU065767	KF611768	FJ937193
Bathymodiolinae	<i>Idas</i>	SAL1	DQ340794	DQ863944	KF611761	DQ340775
Bathymodiolinae	<i>Idas</i>	ESU P	KF611721	GU065846	KF611762	FJ937222
Bathymodiolinae	<i>Idas</i>	<i>washingtonius</i>	AF221645	AY781146	HF545073	AY275546
Bathymodiolinae	<i>Idas</i>	ESU O	KF611722	GU065763	KF611763	FJ937211
Bathymodiolinae	<i>Idas</i>	ESU K	KF611723	GU065868	KF611764	FJ937192
Bathymodiolinae	<i>Idas</i>	<i>argenteus</i> LD	LM992894	LM992896	Not available	LM992892
Bathymodiolinae	<i>Idas</i>	<i>argenteus</i> MAR	LM992893	LM992895	Not available	LM992891
Bathymodiolinae	<i>Terua</i>	<i>arcuatilis</i>	KF611719	GU065879	KF611756	FJ937033
Bathymodiolinae	<i>Terua</i>	ESU T	KF611720	GU065804	KF611757	FJ937283
Bathymodiolinae	<i>Tamu</i>	<i>fisheri</i>	AF221642	AY781132	HF545065	AY649803
Bathymodiolinae	<i>"Lignomodiolus"</i>	SAL4	DQ340796	DQ863947	KF611741	DQ340776
Bathymodiolinae	<i>"Lignomodiolus"</i>	ESU R	KF611708	GU065877	KF611742	FJ937239
Bathymodiolinae	<i>"Lignomodiolus"</i>	ESU S"	KF611707	GU065829	KF611740	FJ937258
Bathymodiolinae	<i>"Lignomodiolus"</i>	ESU Q	KF611709	GU065875	KF611743	FJ937230
Bathymodiolinae	<i>"Lignomodiolus"</i>	ESU G	KF611710	GU065778	KF611744	FJ937161
Bathymodiolinae	<i>Nypamodiolus</i>	ESU I	KF611716	GU065774	KF611754	FJ937188
Bathymodiolinae	<i>Nypamodiolus</i>	<i>japonicus</i> (ESU H)	KF611717	GU065856	KF611755	FJ937073
Bathymodiolinae	<i>Nypamodiolus</i>	ESU J	KF611715	GU065842	KF611753	FJ937189
Bathymodiolinae	<i>Nypamodiolus</i>	<i>samadiae</i>	ON508870	ON508873	ON508854	ON491594

Bathymodiolinae	<i>Nypamodiolus</i>	<i>longissimus</i>	DQ340798	DQ863945	KF611752	DQ340773
Bathymodiolinae	<i>Nypamodiolus</i>	<i>simpsoni</i>	KF611731	KF611700	KF611773	KF611695
Bathymodiolinae	<i>Bathymodiolus</i>	<i>puteoserpentis</i>	AF221640	AY781151	HF545053	AY649796
Bathymodiolinae	<i>Bathymodiolus</i>	<i>azoricus</i>	AY649822	AY781148	KF611758	AY649795
Bathymodiolinae	<i>Bathymodiolus</i>	<i>heckerae</i> BR	AY649830	AY781139	Not available	AY649793
Bathymodiolinae	<i>Bathymodiolus</i>	<i>brooksi</i> AC	AY649826	AY781136	NC_059706	AY649797
Bathymodiolinae	<i>Bathymodiolus</i>	<i>(brevior)</i>	AY649824	AY781150	KX713195	AY649799
Bathymodiolinae	<i>Bathymodiolus</i>	<i>septemdiarium</i>				
Bathymodiolinae	<i>Bathymodiolus</i>	<i>(marisindicus)</i>	AY649818	AY781147	NC_059708	AY275543
Bathymodiolinae	<i>Bathymodiolus</i>	<i>septemdiarium</i>				
Bathymodiolinae	<i>Bathymodiolus</i>	<i>thermophilus</i> A	AF221638	AY781141	HF545052	AF456285
Bathymodiolinae	<i>Gigantidas</i>	<i>mauritanicus</i>	KF611712	FJ890504	KF611747	FJ890502
Bathymodiolinae	<i>Gigantidas</i>	<i>childressi</i>	AF221641	AY781137	DQ177885	AY649800
Bathymodiolinae	<i>Gigantidas</i>	<i>tangaroa</i>	AY649820	AY781134	KF611748	AY608439
Bathymodiolinae	<i>Gigantidas</i>	<i>taiwanensis</i>	KF611711	GU966641	KF611746	GU966638
Bathymodiolinae	<i>Gigantidas</i>	<i>gladius</i>	AY649821	AY781149	HF545085	AY649802
Bathymodiolinae	<i>Gigantidas</i>	sp. 2 Broken Bay	KF611713	KF611697	KF611749	KF611692
Bathymodiolinae	<i>Bathymodiolus</i>	<i>manusensis</i>	KF611718	GU966642	KY270856	GU966637
Bathymodiolinae	<i>"Nipponiomodiolus"</i>					
Bathymodiolinae	<i>Bathymodiolus</i>	<i>aduloides</i>	Not available	HF545036	HF545060	HF545118
Bathymodiolinae	<i>"Nipponiomodiolus"</i>					
Bathymodiolinae	<i>Adipicola</i>	<i>crypta</i> B"	KF611714	EU683298	KF611750	EU702319
Bathymodiolinae	<i>Vulcanidas</i>	ESU E	KF611704	GU065791	KF611736	FJ937079
Bathymodiolinae	<i>Vulcanidas</i>	ESU F	KF611705	GU065809	KF611737	FJ937127
Bathymodiolinae	<i>Vulcanidas</i>	SAL3	DQ340800	DQ863946	KF611738	DQ340772
Bathymodiolinae	<i>Vulcanidas</i>	<i>insolatus</i>	KF611706	FJ767937	KF611739	FJ767936
Bathymodiolinae	<i>Benthomodiolus</i>	<i>lignocola</i>	AF221648	AY781131	KF611733	AY275545
Bathymodiolinae	<i>Benthomodiolus</i>	sp. South Atlantic	KF611703	KF611698	KF611733	KF611691
Bathymodiolinae	<i>Benthomodiolus</i>	sp. Juan de Fuca	KF611702	KF611699	KF611734	KF611694
Modiolinae	<i>Modiolus</i>	<i>auriculatus</i>	KY081336	KY081360	Not available	KY081298
Modiolinae	<i>Modiolus</i>	<i>rumphii</i>	KC429330	KC429423	KC429248	KC429094
Modiolinae	<i>Modiolus</i>	<i>modiolus</i>	KF611701	EF526455	KF611732	FJ890501
Lithophaginae	<i>Leiosolenus</i>	<i>curtus</i>	AB201235	AB103123	JQ267791	AB076944
Lithophaginae	<i>Leiosolenus</i>	<i>mucronata</i>	KY081333	KY081357	KY081317	KY081297
Lithophaginae	<i>Leiosolenus</i>	<i>lima</i>	KY081331	KY081354	KY081316	KY081294
Mytilinae	<i>Mytilus</i>	<i>edulis</i>	KC429331	KC429424	KC429249	KC429095

Supplementary Table ST2: Morphometric measurements of the valves of the *Vadumodiolus teredinicola* type series.

Specimen Code	OGL:Genomic:ID	MCZ:Mala:ID	Length (mm)	Height (mm)	Length/Height Ratio	Designation	Figure
6317L-A	36415	399936	10.75	2.86	3.76	paratype	3d
6317L-B	36416	399937	10.23	3.08	3.32	holotype	3a
6317L-C	36417	399938	8.59	2.75	3.12	paratype	3c, 4
6317L-D	36418	399939	9.43	2.57	3.67	paratype	3b
6317L-E	36419		9.95	2.76	3.61	paratype	
6317L-F	36420		9.33	2.15	4.34	paratype	
6317L-G	36420		7.33	1.65	4.44	paratype	
6317L-H	36420		8.29	2.55	3.25	paratype	
6317L-I	36420		7.89	1.82	4.34	paratype	
6317L-J	36420		5.56	1.57	3.54	paratype	
6317L-K	36420		7.2	1.78	4.04	paratype	
6317L-L	36420		5.4	1.51	3.58	paratype	
6317L-M	36420		5.93	2.09	2.84	paratype	
6317L-N	36420		6.9	1.74	3.97	paratype	
6317L-O	36420		6.7	1.8	3.72	paratype	
6317L-P	36420		7.78	2.11	3.69	paratype	
6317L-Q	36420		7.68	2.25	3.41	paratype	
6317L-R	36420		5.15	1.45	3.55	paratype	
6317L-S	36420		5.63	1.93	2.92	paratype	
6317L-T	36420		6.47	1.6	4.04	paratype	
6317L-U	36420		3.45	1.22	2.83	paratype	
<i>n</i> =21	average		7.41	2.06	3.62		
	standard deviation		1.89	0.53	0.47		

OGL, Ocean Genome Legacy; MCZ, Museum of Comparative Zoology

Supplementary Table ST3: CheckM statistics for various *Vadumodiolus teredinicola* gill bacterium genome assemblies and other related bacteria.

Genome Assembly	Percent Completeness	Percent Contamination	Percent Strain Heterogeneity	%GC Content	Contigs	Genome Size (bp)	N50 (bp)
<i>Vadumodiolus teredinicola</i> (MAG) by metaBAT2 binning	55.09	0.13	0	39.11	237	628,036	2,629
<i>Vadumodiolus teredinicola</i> (MAG) by BLAST searches	87.80	2.78	20	38.43	588	1,008,987	2,301
<i>Vadumodiolus teredinicola</i> (MAG) by combining bin and BLAST searches (final draft assembly)	87.88	2.82	16.67	38.42	611	1,060,823	2,316
<i>Bathymodiolus azoricus</i> BazSymAV2 GCF_001298715.1	97.68	0	0	37.57	515	1,859,850	5,874
<i>Bathymodiolus septemdierum</i> Mjoyin Knoll AP013042	98.68	0	0	38.74	Closed-circular	1,469,434	Not applicable
<i>Bathymodiolus thermophilus</i> EPRN9N CP024634	97.19	1.99	100	38.56	Closed-circular	2,832,685	Not applicable
<i>Ca. Ruthia magnifica</i> CP000488	94.16	0	0	34.03	Closed-circular	1,160,782	Not applicable
<i>Ca. Vesicomysocius okutanii</i> HA AP009247	93.54	0	0	31.59	Closed-circular	1,022,154	Not applicable
<i>Ca. Vesicomysocius endoextente</i> GCA_013416595.1	92.73	0	0	31.09	2	1,021,947	604,961
<i>Ca. Thioglobus autotrophicus</i> EF1 CP010552	99.17	0	0	39.10	Closed-circular	1,512,449	Not applicable

Supplementary Table ST4: Comparison between the final draft genome of *Vadumodiolus teredinicola* gill bacterium and genomes of bathymodiolin thioautotrophic symbionts.

Properties	<i>Vadumodiolus teredinicola</i> (by binning and BLAST)	<i>Bathymodiolus azoricus</i> BazSymAV2	<i>Bathymodiolus septemdiarium</i> Mjoyin Knoll	<i>Bathymodiolus thermophilus</i> EPRN9N
NCBI assembly accession #	JASISB000000000	GCF_001298715.1	AP013042	CP024634
Genome size	1,060,823	1,859,850	1,469,434	2,832,685
Contigs	611	515	Closed-circular	Closed-circular
Percent completeness	87.88%	97.68%	98.68%	97.19%
Percent contamination	2.82%	0.00%	0.00%	1.99%
Strain heterogeneity	16.67%	0.00%	0.00%	100%
%GC	38.42%	37.57%	38.74%	38.56%
% coding density	86.07%	88.89%	93.65%	89.37%
Total number of genes	966	1,946	1,561	2,172
Protein coding genes (CDS)	948	1,906	1,523	2,067
rRNA genes	2 (5S not detected, 16S, 23S)	3 (5S, 16S, 23S)	3 (5S, 16S, 23S)	3 (5S, 16S, 23S)
Sulfide-quinone oxidoreductase (sqr)	yes	no	yes	yes
Adenylyl-sulfate reductase (alpha and beta subunits)	alpha subunit only	alpha and beta subunits	alpha and beta subunits	alpha and beta subunits
Ribulose biphosphate carboxylase/oxygenase (RuBisCO)	small and large subunits	small and large subunits	large subunit only	small and large subunits
Hydrogenase (<i>hupL</i>)	no	yes	yes	yes
Nitrogenase (<i>nifH</i>)	no	no	no	no

Supplementary Table ST5: GenBank accession records of bathymodiolin symbionts and related bacteria that were used in Figures 6 and Supplementary Figure SF5

Genome	NCBI accession #
<i>Vadumodiolus teredinicola</i> gill bacterium (MAG) combined bin and BLAST searches (final draft assembly)	JASISB000000000
<i>Bathymodiolus azoricus</i> BazSymAV2	GCF_001298715.1
<i>Bathymodiolus septemdierum</i> Mjoyin Knoll	AP013042
<i>Bathymodiolus thermophilus</i> EPRN9N	CP024634
<i>Ca. Ruthia magnifica</i>	CP000488
<i>Ca. Vesicomysocius okutanii</i> HA	AP009247
<i>Ca. Vesicomysocius</i> SY067_SCS001	CP054877
<i>Ca. Vesicomysocius</i> endoextente	GCA_013416595.1
<i>Ca. Thioglobus autotrophicus</i> EF1	CP010552
<i>Ca. Thiodiazotropha lotti</i> MAGLRAP2	GCA_016842125.1
<i>Ca. Thiodiazotropha endoloripes</i>	GCA_001709035.1
<i>Ca. Thiodiazotropha taylori</i> MAG	GCA_016842995.1
<i>Ca. Thiodiazotropha</i> Codakia orbicularis	GCA_018619755.1
<i>Ca. Thiodiazotropha</i> endolucinida COS	GCA_001715975.1
<i>Ca. Thiodiazotropha</i> endolucinida	GCA_016842515.1
<i>Ca. Endoriftia persephone</i> strain Guaymas	GCA_013523235.1
<i>Ca. Endoriftia persephone</i> strain Hot96	GCA_000168735.1
<i>Sedimenticola selenatireducens</i> DSM 17993	GCA_000428045.1
<i>Sedimenticola thiotaurani</i> SIP-G1	CP011412
<i>Ca. Sedimenticola</i> endophacoides	GCA_003062205.1
<i>Chrysomallon squamiferum</i> (scaly-foot snail) endosymbiont	AP012978
<i>Kuphus polythalamius</i> endosymbiont <i>Thiosocius teredinicola</i> 2141T	CP019936
<i>Solemya pervernicosa</i> gill symbiont WH SV	GCF_002021235.1
<i>Thiocapsa marina</i> 5811	GCA_000223985.2
<i>Thiocapsa bogorovii</i> BBS	GCA_021228795.1
<i>Allochromatium vinosum</i> DSM 180	GCA_000025485.1
<i>Allochromatium tepidum</i> NZ	GCA_018409545.1
<i>Marichromatium purpuratum</i> 984	GCA_000224005.3
<i>Marichromatium gracile</i> DSM 203	GCA_004343155.1
<i>Solemya pervernicosa</i> gill symbiont Sp-SM6	GCA_002020875.1
<i>Osedax</i> symbiont Rs1	GCA_000416275.1
<i>Thiothrix nivea</i> DSM 5205	GCA_000260135.1
<i>Thiomicrothrix</i> sp. Kp2	GCF_000478585.1
<i>Thiomicrothrix</i> sp. Milos-T2	GCF_000702325.1
<i>Thiomicrothrix arctica</i> DSM 13458	GCF_000381085.1
<i>Thiomicrothrix chilensis</i> DSM 12352	GCF_000483485.1
<i>Hydrogenovibrio kuenenii</i> DSM 12350	GCF_000526715.1
<i>Hydrogenovibrio halophilus</i> DSM 15072	GCF_000384235.1
<i>Thioalkalimicrobium aerophilum</i> AL3	CP007030
<i>Thioalkalimicrobium cyclicum</i> ALM1	CP002776